

EARTH SCIENCES

CURRENT CONTROL AND ACCURACY ANALYSIS OF GEODESIC OBSERVATION RESULTS

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Abstract

Currently, not only probability theory, but also mathematical statistics have found wide application in geodesy. Here, the methods and methods for analyzing the results of observation, their accuracy and homogeneity according to the center of grouping are considered. Various criteria and methods are used for the analysis of observation results, but the simplest methods should be applied in production conditions.

The selection of the number of observations is considered to ensure the reliability and necessary accuracy of the numerical characteristics of the distribution of measurement results.

Keywords: geodetic measurements, regular errors, measurement results.

It is known that the most important rock for all measurements is their accuracy. The degree of accuracy of measurements is characterized by the threshold values of their errors. As we know, measurement error is the difference between the actual value of the measured object and its result. The complexity in determining the errors of measurements is that the estimate of the "true" value of the quantity is obtained from the measurement results in practice [1]. Therefore, the true value of the measured object can be viewed theoretically as any scientific abstraction, and then their estimation can be carried out by the necessary methods. They divide the total error of each measurement and its component into two constituents: regular and random.

A regular constituent remains constant during observations or changes depending on the change of some non-random factor. If in the process of observations some non-random factors change and cannot be recorded, the influence of these factors increases both regular and random organizers. A random component varies randomly from observation to observation: it arises from multiple factors, the influence of which manifests itself in different ways in repeated measurements.

For specific conditions, the random error of each possible measurement can be estimated by determining the limit deviation from the center of the scatter. The latter is calculated to one or another credibility [2, 3].

Let's assume that the distribution of numerical values of observation results of any geodetic object follows the normal law $N(x, \alpha, \sigma)$. Let's consider the value of parameter σ known for a specific set of observations γ (instrument, methods, average length of sides, physical-geographical conditions, etc.), that is, as previously performed production measurements. In the process of geodetic observations, it is necessary to use such criteria for the analysis of the accuracy of the current preventive control and measurement results that the amount of calculation work is reduced to a minimum. Accuracy control can be performed by comparing the $R_{p,n}$ theoretical-probability value of the R_n variation width of the observation results.

Therefore, it is necessary to determine the methodology for determining the theoretical-

probability value (upper limit). The range of variation $R_{p,n}$ is found based on the known parameter σ , the number of observations n and the given probability

$$\alpha = \frac{P}{100}.$$

It is known that the accuracy of geodetic measurements is characterized by the value of the parameter σ . There are different approaches for estimating this parameter obtained from measurement results [4,5,6]. The most effective and unshifted σ^2 variance estimate is the σ^2 empirical variance, the latter calculated using the following formula.

$$\frac{n}{n-1} s^2 = \bar{s}^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \quad (1)$$

s^2 empirical numerical characteristic is a random quantity. Using the distribution of the empirical variance s^2 and taking into account the number of observations n , we can construct a confidence interval for σ^2 with a certain confidence α .

Of course, it can be used in other formulas to estimate the accuracy of measurements under certain conditions. It is quite clear that the accuracy of measuring zenith distances with precision instruments (in trigonometric leveling) is the following formula:

$$q^2 = \frac{1}{2(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} d_i^2 \quad (2)$$

should be evaluated by the method of successive differences. This formula can be applied in other measurements as well, when the center of gravity shifts during the observation process. In case of double measurements

$$\bar{s}^2 = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{i=1}^m d_i^2 \quad (3)$$

formula can be used, where it is stipulated that the measurement results do not contain regular errors.

The result. They try to exclude regular errors from measurement results by one or other methods or include corrections due to the influence of non-random factors. Despite these, it is impossible to completely exclude random error from the observation results [7]. The lack of regular error in the measurement results can

only be imagined as a theory. As a rule, there are random errors in the real measurement results, here we conditionally consider that the value of the regular error in the measurement results is insignificant compared to the random error.

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